

Technical Notes: Pest Monitoring Workbook

Accompanies: “Data-Driven Defence: Evolving Pest Management Practices at Tāmaki Paenga Hira Auckland Museum”

Introduction

This document provides technical guidance on the structure, logic and use of the Excel-based pest monitoring workbook developed by Tāmaki Paenga Hira Auckland Museum. It is intended for other museum colleagues looking to adopt or adapt a similar system for their own institutions.

The workbook was designed to facilitate pest monitoring as part of an Integrated Pest Management (IPM) plan in a museum context. It consolidates departmental data entry, automates key calculations, and provides clear visual summaries to support strategic decision-making. These notes outline the workbook’s design and offer practical tips for implementation and adaptation.

Please note that names, dates, and quantities shown in screenshots are illustrative data only.

Original Workbook

	A	B	C	D	E	F	FC	LN	LV	LY
1			Date:	14/10/11	17 October 2011 -	4 November 2011 -	29/04/2015	13/09/2017	11/10/2017	24/10/2017
2	Room:	Location:	Name on Trap:	Alessandra Barrera	Skyler	Savannah & Kash		Kashlon Chambers	Kiaan S	Mia Keith
3	COLLECTIONS IMAGING									
12										
13	F36 [Applied Arts Workroom]	In the far left hand corner of the room between	F36 TRAP 1				clean	clear	1x adult silverfish	
14	F36 [Applied Arts Workroom]	On the right as you enter the room, on the floor	F36 TRAP 2				clean	clear	in - changed due to date	
15	F36 [Applied Arts Workroom]	On the right as you enter the room, on the floor	INTRODUCED 16/10/2013 - F36 TRAP 3				clean			
16	F36 [Applied Arts Workroom]	On the right as you enter the room, on the floor	INTRODUCED 16/10/2013 - F36 TRAP 4				clean			
17	F36 [Applied Arts Workroom]	To the right of the door into the store	Dermestid Monitor 1 installed 16/08/18							
18	G20 [hotonui]	In the left of the door frame, between the por	G20 TRAP 1				clean	1 small midge fly	sp found. Trap replaced	
19	G57 [Carving]	On the ground floor, in the far left corner as y	G57 TRAP 1	TRAP INSTALLED		see notes in date column	clean	clean	x little orange spider	
20	G57 Meas [Carving]	On the mezzanine level, at the corner and safe	G57 TRAP 2	TRAP INSTALLED		see notes in date column	clean			
21	G57 [Carving]	On the ground floor, at the far end of the stor	G57 TRAP 3	TRAP INSTALLED		see notes in date column	clean	2 and fluffy new tr	clean	
22	G57 [Carving]	On the mezzanine level at the top of the stair	INTRODUCED 16/06/2013 141 G57 Trap 4				clean	clean	1x adult silverfish	
23	G57 [Carving]	To the left of the double doors leading into th	INTRODUCED 16/10/2013 G57 Trap 5				clean	base silverfish 2 adols, 1x little orange spider		
	G57 [Carving]	To the right of the double doors leading into t	INTRODUCED 16/10/2013 G57 Trap 6 DID NOT REPLACE THIS TRAP 6 March 2019. ROOM BEING DECONSTRUCTED AND TRAP GETS MOVED				clean	clear	2 adult silverfish	
24										
177	MAORI DEVELOPMENT TEAM									
178	J27	On ground against far end of right wall, by 02	Introduced: 15/08/2016 J27 TRAP 1							1 x silverfish
179	J27	Dermestid Beetle Larvae Monitoring Trap pla	INTRODUCED: 25/09/2017 J27 TRAP 2							Clean and replaced
180	ISS	On ground at 155 stairwell landing, behind dis	INTRODUCED: 15/08/2016. DISCONTINUED: 8/06/2017 ISS TRAP 1							
181	MONITORING									
182	G15 Non Collection Store	Back right corner of store	G15 Trap 1							
212	Loading Dock	UV light trap (changed out by Ecology)								

Figure 1 Screenshot of the original Excel-based pest monitoring workbook.

The initial Excel pest monitoring workbook had several issues with its layout:

- Manual colour coding: The workbook relied on manual formatting for colour coding, rather than using Conditional Formatting. The only exception was an

orange “Cell Value contains ‘x’” rule which was fragmented into 17 separate cell ranges, making it difficult to manage and update.

- Pre-pivoted data layout: Instead of being stored in a simple “flat” table (where each column represents one type of information, like “Name” or “Date”), the data was already arranged in a way that looks like the *result* of a pivot table. For example, names and dates were spread across the top two rows, rather than sitting neatly in two dedicated columns. This makes it very difficult to report on the data, because it isn’t structured properly for analysis. In a better setup, the names and dates would sit in their own columns, and the summarised layout you want would then be produced using a pivot table, not built into the raw data. *If your raw data already looks like a pivot table, it’s in the wrong format.* See the Data Entry Sheets section below.
- Mixed data types: columns, and even individual cells, contained multiple data types. For instance, Departments should have been in their own dedicated column and the dates in row were mixed with additional notes, making data extraction difficult.
- Lack of data validation: There was no validation applied to critical fields like the Data and Name rows. This allowed for inconsistencies and typos, as seen in various examples such as these:

Tomas Luna & Caleb Kline	Sav /Kash
Tomas Luna & Caleb Kline	Savannah & Kash
Skyler (EVENTS CENTRE CHECK)	Savannah/ Kash
Quinn (on Behalf on Felicity)	Savannah/Kash
Kiaan S	Kash & Savannah
Kiaan S /	Kash and Savannah
Kiaan S.	Kash/Savannah

These layout and formatting errors make this data unreportable, especially for managers looking for summaries of the pest management metrics.

Current Workbook

Structure

The workbook is divided into six categories:

- Departmental data entry sheets
- Overview sheet
- Archive sheet
- Reporting sheets
- Lookup tables sheet
- Print sheets

Data Entry Sheets

Department	Room Number	Room Name	Trap Number	Location	Category	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status: Pests / Clean	Comments	Silver fish	Booklice	Carpet beetle	Cockroach	Spider	Small flying insects	Other	Other (description)	POI
Human History	G20	Hotunui	1	Front right corner	Gallery	5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests		2				2	1	23	springtails	16.2037
Human History	GM39	Midden store	1	To the left of the	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean		5					2	18		146.9724
Human History	H111	Pacific Stairwell	1	Stairwell betw	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Pests							1	2	Midgefly and sp	0.8354
Human History	H21	Pacific Store	2	Underneath fir	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Pests					1			2	springtails	0.4740
Human History	H21	Pacific Store	1	Placed near the	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Pests										0.0000
Human History	H86	HH Library	1	To the left of th		5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean										0.0000
Human History	HM5	Pacific Upstairs	1	Halfway down		5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean										0.0000
Human History	I104	Ceramics store	1	To the left of th	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Pests								1	springtail	0.6430
Human History	I105	HH Arts Workroom	2	In corner by sli	Office Space	5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests		1						2	springtails	0.7150
Human History	I105	HH Arts Workroom	1	To the right of	Office Space	5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests			1							0.7283

Figure 2: Screenshot of current version of pest monitoring workbook, showing a typical departmental input sheet (some pest columns are hidden).

Each department has a dedicated sheet for entering pest counts per trap location.

The current version of the pest monitoring workbook, as shown in the screenshot of a typical departmental input sheet, incorporates several improvements for data entry and integrity.

The blue cells at the beginning of each row list the room and monitor (trap) IDs, and their locations. There is a row for each monitor.

To the right of the table are **formula columns** which calculate various metrics for use in pivot table reports. Some formulas use the data in tables on the Lookup sheet.

- POI
- Total pests per room (i.e. all monitored species)
- Pests
- Non-pests
- Month (in Year, Month, Month-name format: “2025-09 (September)”)
- Year
- Room number and name (“GM39 (Ground Mezzanine 7)”)
- Category (this allows high-level reporting and shows what type of room is the highest risk).

These columns should be hidden to reduce visual clutter. All of the sheet is locked, except data entry cells, so only the Administrator can make changes.

Cell validation is applied to force the correct date format, the correct spelling of the checkers' names, and the monitor's status. The pest columns are forced to only allow whole numbers. The yellow columns ("Comments" and "Other (description)") are unvalidated free-text cells, allowing users to input notes and comments as required.

Conditional formatting is used to highlight any potential issues:

- The Status column highlights any mismatches between the selected status and the pest numbers (for example, when the Status is "Clean", but pest numbers have been added to the same row).
- The pest cells change colour if the number of any pest is greater than the preset limit, providing an immediate visual alert.
- The "Other (description)" field highlights any added text, drawing attention to additional notes.

Overview Sheet and VBA code

Department	Missing data	Mandatory fields to fill	Traps records to remove
Collection Care	70	93	2
Documentary Heritage	45	60	0
Galleries	0	60	0
Human History	39	39	0
Natural Sciences	57	57	0

Figure 3 Overview table with Copy button

The table on this sheet tracks four main metrics:

1. The Department field has links to all the departmental data entry pages for ease of navigation.
2. There are three fields that must be filled completely: Date, Name, and Status. The "Missing data" field shows how many cells are still empty. In the example below, there is a missing date and checker, but the comments tell us why. Because these cells are used in calculations and reporting, they should be filled

anyway. Suitable conditional formatting and/or cell validation would highlight when such compulsory fields need completing. The “Copy Input Data” button will not work until all the cells in “Missing data” are zero; it instead pops up an error message with instructions.

a.

Location	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status : Pests / Clean	Comments	Silver
at corner rch (you ft of the n			Not checked	Closed due to asbestos	
	2/07/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests		

- The “Department count” gives the total number of cells in the three columns in each data entry sheet that need to be filled.
- The “Traps records to remove” field counts the number of traps that checkers list as Missing or Removed. If the trap is missing, it could just be replaced in the same position, instead.

The Administrator checks that all data is entered and that there are no errors, then clicks the yellow “Copy Input data to master sheet” button. This copies all the Department Input sheets to the Archive sheet and resets the Input sheets.

This sheet is protected to prevent unauthorised users breaking it. Background code prohibits use of the “Copy Input data to master sheet” button until all the missing data is added. To prevent non-Administrators using the button, background code authenticates only specified users based on their computer login username.

```
Select Case sUser
Case "gxxxxx", "axxxxx", "mxxxxx", "pxxxxx"
```

The file format must be “.xlsm” or “.xlsb” to allow macros (code) to run; “.xlsb” makes for a smaller file.

Archive Sheet

Department	Room #	Room Name	Trap Number	Location	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status : Pests / Clean	Comments	Silverfish	Ant	Spider	Small flying insect (drain fly, midge, fruit fly)	Other	Other (description)	POI	Total pests per room	Pests	Non-pests	Month	Year	Room	Category
Galleries	#94	Stairwell	4	Behind lift	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Removed								0.00000	0	0	0	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#94 (Stair Gallery	
Galleries	#96	Tree Gallery	9	Under the	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Missing - replaced								0.00000	0	0	0	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#96 (Tree Kitchen	
Galleries	#10	Origins Galle	1	South-wet	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Pests				1	1	6	springtails	-0.18896	8	0	8	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#10 (Orig Gallery	
Galleries	#10	Origins Galle	2	North-wet	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Pests				1		6	springtails	-0.18534	7	0	7	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#10 (Orig Gallery	
Galleries	#10	Origins Galle	3	Under the	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Pests				2		19	1 x click beetle 18 x s	-0.49603	21	0	21	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#10 (Orig Gallery	
Galleries	#4	Maori Natur	1	Far Left co	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Pests						16	springtails	-0.84034	16	0	16	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#4 (Maori Gallery	
Galleries	#4	Maori Natur	2	Under the	Monday, 10 February 2025	Georgia Miller	Pests						2	springtails	-0.10504	2	0	2	2025-02 (Febru	2025	#4 (Maori Gallery	

Figure 4 Screenshot of the Archive table

The Archive sheet serves as the central repository for all data collected from the individual department input sheets.

Every month the administrator uses the “Copy Input Data...” button to transfer the results from the individual department sheets to the Archive sheet’s table. For simplicity, this table has the same layout as the department sheets.

In our current workbook we have records going back to 2011. This allows us to analyse and report on any level of detail required, providing long-term insights into the data.

Rodent Monitoring

Department	Room #	Room Name	Trap Number	Location	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status : Pests / Clean	Comments
Collection Care - Rodent	E7	B2 Stairwell	1	E7 stairwell (access	Wednesday, 2 July 2025	Georgia Miller	RM no activity	
Collection Care - Rodent	E3	B2 Stairwell	2	E3 stairwell (stairwe	Wednesday, 2 July 2025	Georgia Miller	RM no activity	
Collection Care - Rodent	F4	B1 Landing	3	Against the wall bet	Wednesday, 2 July 2025	Georgia Miller	RM activity - bait changed	
Collection Care - Rodent	F52	B1 Corridor	4	Under fire extinguis	Wednesday, 2 July 2025	Georgia Miller	Damaged - Replaced	
Collection Care - Rodent	F34	B1 Corridor	5	Near photography c	Wednesday, 2 July 2025	Georgia Miller	RM no activity	

Figure 5 Rodent monitoring data entry table.

For monitoring rodent bait stations within the Museum, we utilise a modified version of the standard data entry template. This template omits the typical "pest" columns, focusing specifically on rodent-related metrics. If desired, it would be easy to include other metrics like type of bait, activity noted, bait changed (the frequency of this could indicate higher activity at that station), etc.

Department	Internal / External	Room Number	Room Name	Trap Number	Location	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Activity: Yes/No	Bait Changed: Yes/No	Type of Bait	Comments	Category
PestCleaners	Internal	G27	Ground 18	29	1929	21/01/2022	PestCleaners	No	Yes	Bromadiolone Bt		Kitchen
Auckland Museum	Internal	F34	Basement Or	6	to the left of the d	17/02/2022	Gabriela Perez	No	No	Pest Off (Brodifacoum)		Other back-of-house
Auckland Museum	Internal	G23	Ground 14	3	to the left of the E	17/02/2022	Gabriela Perez	No	No	Pest Off (Brodifacoum)		Other back-of-house
Auckland Museum	Internal	G27	Ground 18	2	In the kitchen	17/02/2022	Gabriela Perez	No	No	Pest Off (Brodifacoum)		Kitchen
PestCleaners	Internal	G27	Ground 18	29	1929	21/04/2022	PestCleaners	N/A	N/A	Bromadiolone Bt	Not checked by technician as the café was closed	Kitchen
Auckland Museum	Internal	F34	Basement Or	6	to the left of the d	22/04/2022	Gabriela Perez	No	No	Pest Off (Brodifacoum)		Other back-of-house

The data collected for rodent monitoring is distinct from the general pest data. Therefore, all rodent metrics are archived and reported on separately. However, to maintain a unified and reliable data source, all pest and rodent data are entered and

stored within a single workbook, upholding the data management principle of "one source of truth."

Reporting

Figure 6 Screenshot of one reporting pivot table and associated graph.

Pivot tables and associated graphs pull data from the archive table into separate worksheets. These make for easily updated and filtered reports. These reports can be as granular as desired (e.g. specific pests, results across the departments for a chosen month, etc) or encompass the entire archive.

The reports and graphs are ready-made for use in other documents. They can be easily copied and pasted into external files, such as monthly report documents in Microsoft Word.

Lookup Tables (authority lists)

STAFF NAMES		ROOMS				DEPARTMENTS		PESTS		PEST STATUS		
Name	Priority	Room Number	Floor Name	Room Name	Room size	Category	Department	Department	Pest	Pest/non-pest	Status	Priority
Aila Mejia	1	E11	Basement Two	Basement Two 1	1,330.00	Collection store	Collection Care	Collection Care	Ant	Non-pest	Clean	1
Alonso Oliver	1	E11	Basement Two	Basement Two 3	18.00	Collection store	Collection Care	Documentary/Heritage	Bee		Pests	2
Akora David	1	E3	Basement Two	Basement Two 7	17.00	Other back-of-house	Collection Care	Galleries	Bird		Missing - replaced	3
Andy Caron	1	E7	Basement Two	Basement Two 11	17.20	Other back-of-house	Collection Care	Human History	Black Beetle		Missing - not replaced	4
Antonella Gonzalez	1	E8	Basement Two	Basement Two 12	10.40	Collection store	Collection Care - Rodent	Natural Sciences	Borer Beetle	Pest	Removed	5
Antonio Gutierrez	1	E9	Basement Two	Basement Two 13	81.00	Collection store	Collection Care	Natural Sciences	Borer Beetle	Pest	Removed	6

Figure 7 Screenshot of some of the Lookup tables.

The Lookup sheet contains a set of Excel Tables that serve as "one source of truth" for the workbook. These tables function as authority lists, like those in a database, providing a centralised and consistent source of data for the entire workbook.

The tables on this sheet contain lists of data, such as staff names and room metadata. This information is used by formulas and for data validation in other sheets (e.g., to populate drop-down lists), ensuring consistency and accuracy across all data entry.

A key benefit of using these tables is that any formulas referencing them will automatically adjust whenever the data within a lookup table is changed.

Some tables include an optional “Priority” column. This column allows frequently used items to be sorted to the top of the list for convenience, while the remaining items are displayed in alphabetical order. To prevent unauthorised modifications and maintain data integrity, the entire Lookup sheet is protected and can only be edited by an administrator.

In this context, Excel Tables refer to a specific structured feature in Excel that offers enhanced functionality like automatic filtering and sorting, which is distinct from a basic range of cells. This feature is crucial for maintaining the integrity and usability of the lookup lists.

Print Sheets

Department	Name	Date							
Documentary Heritage									
Room Number	Room Name	Location	Trap Number	Comments	Return to Documentary Heritage				
I24	Level Two 12	To the left when entering from I25	1						
		To the right of the door to gallery	2						
I25	Level Two 13	To the right of the door	1						

Figure 8 Screenshot of a sample departmental print sheet based on a pivot table.

Some pest checkers enter data directly into their laptop, whereas others prefer to print the data entry tables to use with a clipboard on their pest checking rounds.

To standardise and facilitate the process of using physical printouts, a hyperlink button on each of the data entry sheets links to a dedicated pivot-table-based “Print” sheet for each department that automatically updates any room data changes and can be manually revised to suit the user’s requirements.

Validation rules

Trap Number	Location	Category	Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status : Pests / Clean	Comments	Silverfish	Small flying insects	Other	Other (description)	POI
1	To the left of the door w	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean		5	2	18		146.9724
1	Front right corner of the	Gallery	5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests		2	1	23	springtails	10.3704
2	Near double door next to		6/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean				14	midges	250.0000
1	Between double doors a		6/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Pests			2		midgeflies	0.1709
1	Behind single door		6/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Missing - replaced		5				89.2857
1	Stairwell between Pacifi	Collection Store	5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Removed			1	2	Midgefly and springtails	0.3505
2	In corner by sliding door	Office Space	5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Not checked		1		2	springtails	0.7150

Figure 9 Screenshot of the result of a dropdown list validation.

The departmental data entry tables use a combination of four cell validation rules to ensure data accuracy and consistency. These rules prevent errors, maintain data integrity, and ensure the information is in a format that can be used for calculations and reporting.

1. Reference to Lookup Tables: This validation prevents users from accidentally overwriting critical data such as room information, formulas, or table headers. It's similar to a list validation but does not provide a dropdown list. This rule is crucial because the reporting pivot tables rely on these header values remaining constant.
2. Date Formatting and Range: This validation ensures that dates are entered in a format that Excel can use for calculations. Excel accepts several date formats, but dates are sometimes in formats (e.g. "12.2.2025") which, in many countries, are treated as text strings by Excel, and cannot be used in date calculations. The dates entered could be limited to, say, "less than tomorrow" to help prevent typos.
3. Dropdown Lists: Dropdown lists restrict data entry to a predefined list of terms. Data can be entered manually or by choosing from the dropdown icon. These are best created by linking to Lookup tables as a source that dynamically adjusts as the source table changes. In the case of staff names, we allow non-List names, but only after a warning appears.
4. Whole Numbers: This rule is applied to the pest species columns to ensure that only whole numbers are entered. This is critical for accurate calculations and prevents the entry of text or decimal values, which would otherwise cause errors in the reporting data.

Formulas

Other (description)	POI	Total pests per room	Pests	Non-pests	Month	Year	Room	Category
	0.00000	0	0	0	2025-02 (February)	2025	H94 (Stairwell)	Gallery
	0.00000	0	0	0	2025-02 (February)	2025	H96 (Tree Gallery)	Kitchen
springtails	0.18896	8	0	8	2025-02 (February)	2025	H10 (Origins Gallery)	Gallery
springtails	0.16534	7	0	7	2025-02 (February)	2025	H10 (Origins Gallery)	Gallery
click beetle	0.49603	21	0	21	2025-02 (February)	2025	H10 (Origins Gallery)	Gallery

Figure 10 Screenshot of the conversion formulas in the Archive sheet.

Formulas in this workbook are strategically used to convert raw data into a format suitable for analysis and reporting. Several of them refer to the Lookup tables, thus reducing the amount of data entry needed and helping ensure consistent data.

Each departmental sheet contains a set of formulas to the right of the main data table. These formulas convert the raw archived data into other metrics that are then used by the reporting pivot tables, like this:

Year summary			
Month	#Pests	#Non-pests	#Total pests per room
2025-01 (January)	48	236	284
2025-02 (February)	11	226	237
2025-03 (March)	14	144	158
2025-04 (April)	7	283	290

Conditional Formatting

Date checked:	Name of pest checker:	Status : Pests / Clean	Comments	Silverfish	Small flying insects	Other	Other (description)
5/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean		5	2	18	
5/02/2025	Philip Hinton	Pests		2	1	23	springtails
6/02/2025	Georgia Miller	Clean				14	midges

Rule (applied in order shown)	Format	Applies to	Stop If True
Cell Value > 5	AaBbCcYyZz	=K\$4:\$T\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cell Value > 10	AaBbCcYyZz	=S\$4:\$Y\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cell does not contain a blank value	AaBbCcYyZz	=Z\$4:\$Z\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>
Formula: =SUM(K4:T4)>0	AaBbCcYyZz	=S\$4:\$S\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>
Formula: =OR(AND(I4="",SUM(K4:Y4)>0),AND(I4="...))	AaBbCcYyZz	=S\$4:\$S\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>
Formula: =OR(MAX(K4:T4)>5,MAX(U4:Y4)>10)	AaBbCcYyZz	=S\$4:\$S\$16	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 11 Screenshot of Conditional Formatting rules for department data entry sheets.

In this workbook, we use Conditional formatting to highlight data entry errors (e.g. “Clean” when pests are also entered) and as an alert if the pest count is over a preset level

Defined Names and Named Ranges

Figure 12 Screenshot of defined names as shown in Excel's Name Box.

Creating Named Ranges for navigation allows a user to jump to the desired sheet by using the Name Box. In the example above, they are prefixed with “_Nav” to bring them to the top of the top of the list and group them.

Other Named Ranges are set for the background code to operate on specific parts of the Departmental sheets. One set selects the whole table for copying to the archive, and another selects only the cells that are to be cleared by the reset code.

Excel gives Tables a default name (“Table1”), but these can also be edited to suit. The lookup tables are prefixed by “LU_” to group them and easily distinguish them from other tables.

Comments

Figure 13 Screenshot of Comment use

Comments are a useful way to give instructions, alert others to an issue, go to cells, etc. They are easy to add and can be notified by email to specific users. They also allow you to assign tasks to yourself or others.

A small purple flag in a cell indicates the presence of a Comment. All the Comments on a sheet can be seen in the Comments Pane (*Review > Comments > Show Comments*). Selecting a Comment will take you to the related cell and vice versa.

Pest Occurrence Index (POI)

We have incorporated the Pest Occurrence Index (POI) into our workbook. The POI is a metric used to standardise pest data. It was developed by Baars and Henderson (2021) to account for variables such as the number of monitors, room size, and exposure time. The formula is defined as:

$$\text{POI} = \frac{\text{pests}_{\text{sum}}}{\text{D} \times \text{E} \times \text{t}}$$

Where:

pests_{sum} = The sum of the occurrences of all pest species observed on each pest monitor.

D = The number of monitors in this room.

E = The room size in square meters (m²).

t = The length of time (in days) of exposure of the monitors in this room between pest checks.

The resulting decimal value is multiplied by 1000 to overcome a "natural number bias," as recommended by Baars and Henderson, to make the number more intuitive to interpret. A larger POI value indicates a higher density of pests relative to the space and time monitored.

In the workbook, this formula is applied to pest monitoring data. The standard Excel version of the formula is:

= pests_{sum} / (number of monitors * room size * number of days) * 1000

number of pests	Traps per room	Room size m2	Previous date checked	Date diff	POI	POI condensed
25	1	6.3	9/01/2025	27.00	146.9724	146.9724

The workbook's design consolidates all the metrics for the POI into a single formula column for efficiency. The formula also allows for the use of Excel's LET function, which assigns names to parts of the formula to improve readability and maintenance:

```

=LET(
  countTraps, COUNTIF([Room '#], [@[Room '#]]),
  roomSize, IFERROR(XLOOKUP([@[Room '#]], LU_RoomCode[Room Code], LU_RoomCode[Room size]), 1),
  dateChecked, [@[Date checked:]],
  prevDate, MAXIFS(Table_ALLDEPT[Date checked:], Table_ALLDEPT[Room '#], [@[Room '#]]),
  dateDiff, dateChecked - prevDate,

  pestSum, SUM(Input_HH@[Silverfish]:[Other])),
  result,

  pestSum / (countTraps * roomSize * dateDiff) * 1000,
  result
)

```

Due to the detailed nature of the captured data, the POI can be calculated not only for the total pest count but also for individual pest species, allowing for highly granular analysis.

Template Access and Use

A redacted version of the pest monitoring workbook is available for downloading [here](#).

This template includes:

- Pre-configured data entry sheets with cell validation and conditional formatting
- A working “Overview” dashboard with error-checking (note that the macro code line *okUser = (sUser = "gmiller") Or (sUser = "phinton") Or (sUser = "Hinton")* will need revision with your username before you can use the Copy button)
- Archive and reporting sheets with pivot tables and sample graphs
- Lookup tables
- Example VBA code for administrative functions

The template is intended to serve as a starting point for other institutions looking to adopt or adapt a similar system. Users are encouraged to modify it according to their own contexts, pest types, and monitoring protocols.

If need be, you're welcome to contact us:

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References

Baars C, Henderson J (2021) Integrated Pest Management: from monitoring to control. In: Integrated Pest Management for Collections Proceedings of 2021: A Pest Odyssey, - The Next Generation, September 2021. Archetype Publications Ltd, London, 142-147.